

Proposed Marketing Mix Strategy for Indonesian Restaurant in The Netherlands (Case Study: Pasundan)

Nadira Karamina¹, Ira Fachira²

^{1,2} School of Business Management, Institute of Technology Bandung

ABSTRACT: Indonesian and Asian culture has had a profound influence on Dutch culture and society due to colonialization. Food is one area where this cultural mix has had a significant impact. Many parts of Indonesian cuisine were adopted and became popular dishes in the Netherlands until now. However, vast number of Indonesian food enthusiasts cannot considerably enhance sales of Pasundan, an Indonesian restaurant in Nijmegen, the Netherlands. Based on analysis of the root cause it was found that some elements from 7P marketing mix, namely Price, Place, Promotion, and Process were the problematic ones. This study aims to generate findings to propose new marketing mix for Pasundan. In order to propose new marketing mix external and internal analysis is performed to gain a comprehensive and in-depth understanding of company difficulties. External analysis focuses on PESTEL, competitor analysis, and online consumer analysis. Marketing Mix (7P) and Segmenting, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) are included in the internal study. The proposed strategies are put together into a new marketing mix plan that is expected to provide a solution to the existing business problem and can be implemented by Pasundan.

KEYWORDS: Marketing Mix, Price, Place, Promotion, Process, Restaurant, Sales, The Netherlands

INTRODUCTION

Following the conclusion of WWII, many Indonesians and Indonesians of Dutch descent immigrated to the Netherlands. During the interbellum, in 1930 many people with a past as a soldier or citizen in the Dutch East-Indies settled in Dutch cities. This diverse mix of people frequently continues to make and consume the dishes they were used to, bringing new recipes and tastes to Europe (Verriet, 2022). The growth of Indonesian cuisine and Indonesian restaurants began when some of the Chinese restaurants that were already present in the Netherlands changed their name to *Chinees-Indisch* in order to capitalize on new market opportunities from the many soldiers who had recently returned from serving many years in Indonesia (Lien, Yoe Sie 2015).

Nowadays Indonesian cuisine is now available in a wide range of Indonesian restaurants and supermarkets throughout the Netherlands. Outside of Indonesia, no other country has an easy access to Indonesian food, spices, and condiments as the Netherlands (Lien, Yoe Sie 2015). In 2013, there were 1,600 Indonesian restaurants in the Netherlands (Ginanjari, 2013). Following that, the Netherlands could serve as a second home for Indonesian cuisine, much like Hong Kong serves as a second home for Japanese cuisine (Baldwin, 2018). According to Retno Marsudi, Indonesian Ambassador in 2013 (Ginanjari, 2013), "Indonesian food is like the second national food in the Netherlands." This condition, combined with the ease of obtaining Indonesian cuisine in the Netherlands, can provide opportunities for the Indonesian restaurant business to expand and grow.

The object used in this study is Pasundan. Pasundan is an Indonesian restaurant located in the city of Nijmegen, Netherlands and has been around for 12 years. Pasundan applies the concept of traditional Indonesian cuisine, so that the taste is authentically Indonesian. However, vast number of Indonesian food enthusiasts in the Netherlands cannot considerably enhance sales of Pasundan for the past periods. This study aims to investigate the current business condition in marketing scope, factors that influencing decline of sales, and develop new marketing strategy for Pasundan.

BUSINESS ISSUE

To make it easier for the author to develop the primary cause categories, the writer uses the 7P marketing mix. Product, people and physical evidence do not show any issues among the 7Ps of marketing mix. Pasundan is even nominated as the Best Vegetarian Restaurant in Nijmegen and also got recommended badge from Restaurant Guru. Despite the restaurant's small size, the author was

unable to locate any bad online reviews and issues that could influence customers' decisions about the restaurant. After dig in to the current issues, the author found that Price, Process, Place, and Promotion are the one causing problems.

Place

In the Netherlands, people can order food online directly through restaurant's website, Uber Eats, and Thuisbezorgd. Pasundan is only available on 2 channels (own website and Thuisbezorgd) and not partnered with Uber Eats. As a result, Pasundan may miss opportunities to attract new prospects from Uber Eats users.

Price

There is a gap between what customer expected and the price charged. Customers may believe that the price is too high for what they receive due to inconsistent quality and a lack of attention to detail, such as providing an incomplete order. If a service's perceived costs exceed its perceived benefits, the service has a negative net value and the consumer is unlikely to buy it (Wirtz and Lovelock, 2021).

Promotion

In terms of promotional strategy, Pasundan only engages in Events & experiences (offline activation). Pasundan is lacking other promotional activities and digital marketing activities to communicate to larger audience. As a result, Pasundan has lack awareness from current and potential audience. Pasundan has not been proactive in maximizing the power of online platforms like Instagram, despite the fact that Nijmegen is teeming with students who are highly active on social media.

Process

During peak hours, the restaurant can be so crowded that orders can come in at the same time via online ordering or by phone. Customers may come to dine in or to order take away as well. However, due to many orders coming at the same time, delivery delays and incomplete orders occurred. There are several negative online reviews that mentioned about the lateness of delivery and incomplete orders.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Service Marketing

Restaurants are included in the service category despite the fact that they deliver a physical product in the form of food and beverages. Services, according to Wirtz & Lovelock (2021), are economic activities performed by one party for another in exchange for money, time, and effort in exchange for desired results from clients. Marketers typically employ the 4Ps of marketing mix while building a strategy for manufacturing products. In the service industry, however, marketers typically employ the 7P marketing mix. This is due to the absence of a customer interface in the traditional marketing mix.

Marketing Mix

Implementing marketing mix activities is critical for allowing business programs and supporting overall company strategy in order to build and sustain competitive advantages for the firm (Cruz-Milan, O., 2022). According to Wirtz and Lovelock (2021), the elements of the 7Ps marketing mix are the seven strategic levers of services marketing that are utilized to build strategies for profitably meeting client demands in competitive marketplaces.

Product

A service product must be able to provide additional value to customers while also solving problems or meeting their demands. Service products are composed of a core product that meets the basic needs of the customer and a number of extra service pieces that are mutually reinforcing and provide value to help consumers utilize the core product more effectively (Wirtz & Lovelock, 2021).

Place

In the restaurant industry, services can be delivered via having clients visit the restaurant or ordering and picking up their food. According to Sedmak (2011), the most prevalent channels of distribution in the restaurant industry are location, direct distribution, and indirect distribution through travel agencies and other suppliers.

Promotion

According to Wirtz and Lovelock (2021), promotion and communication serve three important functions: offering needed information and guidance, persuading target customers to purchase the service product, and urging them to act at specified periods. When it comes to service products, particularly food, there is often ambiguity about the quality, scent, and flavor. As a result, it is critical for restaurants to communicate their service goods by providing clear images of the menus they provide. The role of promotion is to communicate directly or indirectly with individuals, groups, or organizations in order to raise awareness of a product/company and persuade them to get it (Gursoy, 2017).

Price

Wirtz and Lovelock (2021) discussed the psychology of menu pricing in restaurants in their book *Service Marketing*. They argue that prices with dollar signs will result in customers spending less than when there are no dollar signs on the menu; prices that end with "9" will make customers feel like they are getting good value for money; place the most expensive item at the top of the menu; and the most profitable item on the menu should be placed at the top right-hand corner of the page. Moreover, when consumers purchase a service, they evaluate the perceived benefits against the perceived expenses (Wirtz and Lovelock, 2021).

Physical Evidence

The physical environment for a restaurant includes the appearance of the building, interior design, restaurant cleanliness, employee uniforms, food displays, the smell and sound of music in the restaurant.

People

People in restaurants are classified as either customer interface employees (waitresses and waiters) or non-customer interface personnel (cooks, managers, cashiers, and others) (Amofah, *et al.*, 2016). Employees that are loyal, motivated, friendly to customers, and knowledgeable about the products offered can provide restaurants with a competitive advantage.

Process

The process in marketing mix includes the whole food manufacturing process, starting from purchasing raw materials, preparing and cooking the dishes, and delivering the food to customers. Mahmood *et al.*, (2014 cited from Amofah, *et al.*, 2016) stated that a service strategy and training are required to ensure consistency and quality of service

METHODOLOGY

Based on the current business issue, this study is an exploratory research. Exploratory research provides insights into, and an understanding of, the problem confronting the researcher (Polonsky & Waller, 2019). There are two main sources of data which are primary data and secondary data. For qualitative research method, this study will use in-depth interviews, observational methods, literature review. This study also uses external and internal analysis. The external analysis will include PESTEL, Competitor Analysis and Consumer Analysis; and the internal analysis will include STP and Marketing mix.

Data Collection Method

The type of method to be used will depend on the research problem and questions being examined, as this directs the data to be collected (Polonsky & Waller, 2019). This research is using qualitative method. Since the research question requires in-depth understanding of the current issue, hence the qualitative method is chosen. In addition, qualitative method can also be used to gain more insights and understanding from the stakeholders.

Semi-structured interviews using open-ended questions was conducted for this study. Open-ended questions are a means of getting the respondents view, opinions, or descriptions of experiences (Polonsky & Waller, 2019). The unstructured in-depth interview was done with the owners of Pasudan to gain insights of current situation and identify business issue. The structured in-depth interview was also done by asking the questions that author already designed to employees of Pasundan and consumers. The purpose of conducting this interview is so that the author can gain better understanding of the consumer behaviour regarding Indonesian food and restaurants in the Netherlands

According to Polonsky & Waller (2019), secondary data should be taken first as these provide invaluable background information for this research. Secondary data can be gained from internal or external sources. This study also examines the marketing activity through

Pasundan's website and social medias. In order to gain insights of consumers perspectives and behaviour, the author also examines online reviews of Pasundan from Google review, Facebook review, Tripadvisor review and Thuisbezorgd review.

Data Analysis Method

Data analysis is based on the researcher's decision-making processes about evidence identified in the data set (Mills & Birks, 2014). Because this research is considered to be qualitative research and the type of the data gathered is also qualitative, hence this study does not need to use statistic method. To analyze the qualitative data from this research is by using content analysis. Content analysis can be used to analyze the number of frequencies of particular words. Other visual documents such as image can also be examined using content analysis

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

PESTEL Analysis

a. Politic

The Dutch government is considering new legislation that would impose stricter limitations on advertising and fast-food establishments near schools. According to CBS (Statistic Netherlands), half of the adult population is classified as overweight. In an effort to urge Dutch citizens to adopt a healthier lifestyle, the Dutch government implemented the National Prevention Agreement (Seveno, 2022). Because of the strict food and health safety standards, the restaurant must ensure that these regulations are followed in order to avoid fines and penalties. In terms of immigration regulations, the availability of Indonesian chefs and employees may be impacted. Changes in these policies may have an impact on the restaurant's ability to hire the needed employees.

b. Economic

According to the European Commission's economic forecast for the Netherlands, the Dutch economy continues to thrive despite very high inflation. Consumption growth is expected to drop slightly in 2023 as people adjust to higher prices. Russia's action against Ukraine has had ramifications for the Dutch economy, including higher energy prices and increasing uncertainty. In conclusion, people are less likely to eat out during economic downturns, which may have an impact on the restaurant's revenue.

c. Social

Many immigrants travel to the Netherlands in search of a better life, and Dutch people are reported to be understanding of the situation. The Dutch are also quite open to diverse cultures, the LGBT issue, and the usage of substances. This openness can lead to cultural acceptance, which could be beneficial for Indonesian restaurant. According to Terhost & Erkus-Ozturk (2014), the Netherlands along with the USA and UK have a weak national food identity. As a result, people in countries with a weak national food identity are more open to other cuisines (Terhost & Erkus-Ozturk, 2014). Furthermore, a lack of national food identity provides excellent opportunities for immigrant-entrepreneurs to open a restaurant with a home-country kitchen (Terhost & Erkus-Ozturk, 2014). Hence, Indonesian food has opportunity to be accepted by the expat and the locals in Nijmegen. Moreover, there's a changing in food consumption where Dutch people tend to eat healthier by consuming less meat and more vegetables and fruits. With a growing trend towards healthy eating and vegetarianism, the restaurant in the Netherlands may need to adjust its menu to accommodate these preferences.

d. Technology

According to Data Reportal, as of 2023, 88.1% of the Netherlands' total population, which translates to approximately 13.26 million users aged 18 and above, actively engage with various social media platforms. The most used social medias in the Netherlands are Whatsapp, Facebook, and followed by Instagram. Currently there are also many internet users who read online reviews before deciding to use a product or before visiting a place. Therefore, it is important for businesses to maintain good online reviews because online reviews can influence the consumer's decision process in consuming a product

e. Legal/Law

The General Food Law Regulation protects human life and consumer interests in food while maintaining the effective operation of the internal market. To protect consumer health, food businesses must adhere to national safety and sanitary standards. They are legally required to develop a food safety plan based on the Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point (HACCP) approach. The Netherlands has strict employment laws. The restaurant must ensure it adheres to these laws, which

cover areas like working permit, working hours, and wages. The restaurant also must comply with Dutch and EU laws on food labelling and allergen information. Thus, for unwrapped meals, the restaurant must be able to inform the customers about the possible allergens in the dishes. Failure to comply could result in penalties

f. Environment

Since 1 July 2023, the restaurant can't give a single use plastic container for free for their customers. If the restaurant sell take away food or coffee, they must follow rules to use environment friendly packaging.

Competitor Analysis

1. Indian Way

Indian Way is an indirect competitor for Pasundan because it provides a different special menu but has almost the same market. Indian way is pretty active on Instagram to promote their products as well as to announce the current sales promotion. They also employ Google advertisements to optimize their Google searches. Based on Google Review, Indian Way has a score of 4.4 from 492 reviews. Customers who want to buy food online can do so through the company's website, Uber Eats, and Thuisbezorgd.

2. Emmy

Emmy is an authentic Indonesian restaurant located approximately 900 meters from Pasundan. Emmy received 4.6 Google ratings from 161 people. Emmy does not have social media. The only digital marketing activities that are owned are announcements that are updated on the website page. Emmy did not carry out any promotional activities. Consumers cannot order food online because Emmy only accepts dining on the spot.

3. Iwan

Iwan is a restaurant that serves Chinese, Indonesian and Surinamese menus. Iwan got a score of 4.2 out of 138 reviews on Google Reviews. This restaurant only has its own website and does not have an account on social media. Iwan is also available in online food delivery services on the Thuisbezorgd and Uber Eats platforms. In terms of price, Iwan has a slightly cheaper price compared to Pasundan. However, Iwan doesn't have many options for vegetarian or vegan menu

4. Tiffin

Tiffin serves authentic Indonesian food. Tiffin has social media accounts on Instagram and Facebook. Tiffin also has its own website, but the website is rarely updated because the last post was from 2020. The menu options offered are not so many. This restaurant gets a score of 4.5 out of 102 reviews on Google Reviews. However, there are some comments stating that the price offered is too expensive when compared to the quality of the food.

Customer Online Review Analysis

Online reviews are a reliable source of information for customers at restaurants. Customers can form a full idea of the restaurant they intend to visit by reading reviews (Micu et al., 2017). In conducting this analysis, the author reads all the existing reviews from Google Review, Tripadvisor, Facebook and Thuisbezorgd. The author will only generate recent reviews from 2022. First, the author gathers all existing reviews, and then, for the Dutch reviews, the author will translate the review into English. The author then searches for keywords in these reviews. These keywords are then classified into four groups/categories based on the most frequently discussed comments by consumers. This is done to make grouping the data easier. The four categories are Food, People, Price, and Process. After creating this category, the author groups the words used in reviews based on the existing categories. Lastly, the author makes calculation of the words. Because not all of the categories are covered in each review, the author must count the number of answers in each category.

a. Food

The Food category is the most widely discussed by customers on all platforms. The author collects 86 words that describe consumer perceptions of food in Pasundan. This category results in 6 kinds of comments which mainly talk about Taste, Quality, Portion, Menu Variation, Authenticity, and Recommendation. In Food category 79% of the reviews are positive online reviews, the remaining 21% is negative reviews. The words used to describe low quality by customers are "low quality", "bad quality", "meat was dry", "dry food", and "smell horrible". There are three people who are not satisfied with portions in Pasundan. They expect to have bigger portion for the price paid. Another bad review is about the temperature of the food. Three customers mentioned about "cold" and "lukewarm". When it comes to order food online, customers expect

to have a warm food deliver to their door. However, due to the delayed delivery time caused by the high number of orders that came together, the meal became cold because it took too long on the road. Another explanation is that the employee may take less time to warm up the food, resulting in the dish being too cold when it is delivered. To conclude, the majority of customers gave good and positive online reviews in terms of food. The majority of the reviews mentioned about the good taste of the products. Despite the fact that there are reviews that criticize poor food quality, this can be used to be more attentive in presenting the meal and to continue to maintain the taste that is offered

b. Process

In terms of process, the author only creates three groups which is On Time, Late, and Incomplete. 33% of customers who wrote review about delivery are satisfied. The words that they used are “on time”, “excellent”, “fast”, and “faster than expected”. 47% of customers who wrote review about delivery have negative opinions about it. The words that they used are “late”, “took a long time”, and “very late”. Two customers even had to wait for almost two hours to get their food delivered to home. The remaining 20% is customers who complaint about the incomplete order that they received. Another important thing to analyze about delivery is the product itself. The author gathered six reviews from Google Review and Thuisbezorgd page that mentioned about incomplete order. The employees tend to forget to include all orders in one bag.

c. People

People is the third category most talked by customers. The author then grouped the people review into two categories such as Friendly and Good. There is only one negative comment about people on Thuisbezorgd. The disappointed customer left bad review because she tried to contact Pasundan due to the incomplete order, however Pasundan’s team did not respond to her email. On the other hand, the majority of customers left good and positive reviews toward people in Pasundan.

d. Price

There are seven reviews that mentioned about the price in Pasundan. The author then grouped the reviews into two categories, which is Good and Pricey. There are five reviews, which count to 71% of the customers that commented about the price in Pasundan is expensive. The most “pricey” comment can be found on Thuisbezorgd page. Many customers stated that the amount of food they get is not equal to the price they paid. Hence the product is too expensive. If a service's perceived costs exceed its perceived benefits, the service has a negative net value and the consumer is unlikely to buy it (Wirtz and Lovelock, 2021).

STP Analysis

1. Segmentation

To properly segment a market, it is typically essential to begin with a thorough grasp of the demands of the clients. Marketers can then combine this information with demographic, psychographic, and behavioral data to further identify and explain key market categories (Wirtz & Lovelock, 2021).

Table 1. Pasundan’s Segmentation

Geographic Segmentation	
Country	The Netherlands
Province	Gelderland
City	Nijmegen
Demographic Segmentation	
Gender	Male and Female
Age	18 - 64 years old
Occupation	Student, Employees, Housewives, Retiree
Marital	Single and married
Socio-economic Class	SEC C to SEC A
Psychographic/Behavior Segmentation	
Housewives who don't have time for cooking	
Indonesians and Dutch with Indonesian descent who miss Indonesian food	
Tourist who wants to try exotic food in the Netherlands	

2. Targeting

Companies cannot fulfill all existing customers because their needs vary. As a result, organizations must carefully consider which segments to target as their target market. Focus, according to Wirtz & Lovelock (2021), involves delivering a somewhat tight product mix for a certain target segment. Pasundan is only focused on B2C market, hence their current target market is people who live in Nijmegen area. At the moment, they don't have more specific target market and criteria.

3. Positioning

To create a positioning map, the comparison variables used were price and the number of vegetarian/vegan menus offered. The author then compared 4 competitors of Pasundan. The competitors that author chose are other Indonesian restaurants, Chinese-Indonesian restaurant, and indirect competitor of Pasundan. Those competitors also have the same characteristic which is the restaurant have a capacity for dine in.

Figure 1. Positioning Map

Marketing Mix Analysis

a. Product

Pasundan serves authentic Indonesian food. The owner who is also the main chef uses recipes passed down from the family so that the authenticity is guaranteed. Pasundan has more than 30 products on their menu. Pasundan offers menus that are not served by its competitors such as, *Nasi Goreng Ikan Asin*, *Ikan Pepesan*, *Laksa Bogor*, *Mie Bakso*, and many more. However, some of the menus are still unfamiliar to customers. As a result, those special menus don't sell well.

b. Place

The restaurant is located in Nijmegen, a small city in the Netherlands and famous for being called 'Old City, Young Vibe'. The restaurant also located next to Indian restaurant, hence many people mistaken the place due to the similarity of the name in Dutch (*Indische* in Dutch translates to Indian but usually refers to Indonesian food/restaurant). According to preliminary research 33% of respondents prefer Uber Eats than Thuisbezorgd. Those who chose Uber Eats are expats who live in Nijmegen. This is probably because for internationals, Uber Eats are more well-known globally since Thuisbezorgd is a Dutch multinational company. Even though the market share of Thuisbezorgd is still bigger, however Pasundan may miss an opportunity to serve potential customers who prefer Uber Eats.

c. Price

Nijmegen is considered to be student city hence there are many students who live in Nijmegen. Every year Radboud University enrolls 22,000 students. The population in Nijmegen alone in 2022 is 179,000 people. It also means that students make almost 15% of the population. However, the price of Pasundan's products can be expensive for students as they usually have limited budget for living. Inflation in the Netherlands also plays a role in this. Pasundan must raise its prices to compensate the increased costs of materials, energy, and gas. Compared to its competitors, they offer lower price than Pasundan. Customers may see it as cheaper because they serve a smaller portion.

d. Promotion

Every month, Pasundan does a sponsorship for Indonesian movie event in Nijmegen, called Indo Film Café. Another promotion activity that Pasundan does is participating in special event. In terms of distribution of information, Pasundan separate the vegetarian and vegan menu so consumers will not be confused by both. They also put additional information for vegan menu, and pay attention to allergen ingredients. Therefore, customers with diet restriction can be mindful toward their food selection. However, there’s no ‘recommended’ or ‘best seller’ logo in the menu to help customers choose the dishes. Many menus are still unfamiliar for customers and those menus also don’t sell pretty well. Pasundan does not engage in other promotion activities, especially in digital marketing.

e. People

The total employees in Pasundan are nine people, including assistant chef, kitchen staff, front of house staff, and delivery guy. Almost all of the staffs are part time worker, they are high school and university students. The owner is also a main chef who also have Indonesian descent. There is an assistant chef who will come to work every Thursday. Other than that, the main chef works alone on other days. In one day, there are usually 2 people working as front of house staff and kitchen staff, and 1-2 people to deliver the orders. When the staffs made mistake, the owners do not punish them instead they will only inform the staff about customer’s complaint.

f. Physical Evidence

The restaurant has a big window that makes sunlight can get in to the restaurant which gives a natural light in day time. There are pictures and Indonesian traditional stuffs to decorate inside of the restaurant. Pasundan gives cozy and family-vibes kind of restaurant. Their employees usually wear uniform, a black t-shirt with Pasundan’s logo on the chest. Some of the ready-to-serve food is displayed in a citrine. Hence, customers can see directly how the food look like and what to order.

g. Process

Pasundan has several ready-to-eat food menus which can then be warmed up in the microwave before being served or sent to customers. However, there are also foods that must be made directly by the chef, such as *Nasi Goreng Ikan Asin*, *Sop Tahu Pedes*, dan *Laksa Bogor*. Even though many ready-to-eat menus are warmed up in the microwave, the staff still takes time to prepare the side dishes. For example, in preparing *Soto Ayam*, the staff needs to warm it up in a pot and then he has to prepare *lontong*, bean sprouts, spring onions, and boiled egg in a bowl. The customers can enjoy the meal at the restaurant or have it take-away. They can also order the food through phone call, Pasundan’s website, and Thuisbezorgd app/website.

SWOT Analysis

Table 2. SWOT Analysis

Strengths		Weakness	
S1	Authentic Indonesian cuisine	W1	Low awareness from both existing and potential target customers
S2	Pasundan has special Indonesian menus that competitors don't serve	W2	Lack of digital marketing activities
S3	Positive customers review about several aspects	W3	Lack of promotion activities to keep customers interested
S4	Rewarded in 2023 as the Best Vegetarian Restaurant in Nijmegen	W4	Pasundan only has two marketing channels and doesn't have page on Uber Eats
S5	Variety of vegan and vegetarian options	W5	Online negative reviews about some aspects
S6	Longevity		
Opportunity		Threat	
O1	Shift of food consumption in the Netherlands to healthier choice	T1	Inflation in the Netherlands
O2	Dutch people are more open to other cuisines	T2	The regular market can be stagnant and not growing
O3	Popularity of Indonesian food	T3	Competitors with similar products
O4	Large amount of internet and social medias users in the Netherlands	T4	Affordable product prices offered by competitors
O5	Nijmegen is famous for being student city		

TOWS Matrix

Table 3. TOWS Matrix

	Strength	Weakness
	SO Strategies	WO strategies
Opportunity	(SO1) - (S1, S2, S3, S5, S6, O1, O2, O3, O4) Focus on emphasizing brand and product on social media	(WO1) - (W1, W2, W3, W5, O4) WO1 - Improve digital marketing efforts to increase the restaurant's online presence, and capitalize on the large number of internet and social media users in the Netherlands.
	(SO2) - S4, O1, O2, O5 Display the award logo from Restaurant Guru	(WO2) - (W4, O1, O2, O3, O4, Collaborate with platforms like Uber Eats to broaden the distribution channels and reach a wider audience.
	(SO3) S3, S4, S6, O2, O3, O5 Utilize the positive customer reviews and achievement to create a loyal customer	(WO3) - (W5, O4) Actively monitor online review, respond promptly to negative review,
	(SO4) S1, S2, S6, O2, O3 Promote the family recipe and authenticity of the Indonesian cuisine to attract Dutch people who are open to other cuisines.	
Threats	ST Strategies	WT Strategies
	(ST1) - (S3, T3, T4) Use its strong foundation of loyal customers and positive reviews to counter the threat of competitors with similar products.	(WT1) - (W1, W4, T2) Attract new market
	(ST2) - (S1, S3, S4, S6, T1, T3, T4) Maintain the restaurant's reputation for friendly service and high quality food to combat the threat of inflation and potential price increase	(WT2) - (W2, W3, T3, T4) Engage in more promotion activities to beat competitors
		(WT3) - (W2, W3, W5, T2) Review and change the menu on a regular basis to stay up with changing consumer preferences and to avoid stagnation. (WT4) - W5, T3, T4 Establish SOP thus Pasundan can enhance better services to compete with competitors

WT: BIKIN SO

RECOMMENDATIONS

Product

- (WT3) Review and change the menu on a regular basis to stay up with changing consumer preferences and to avoid stagnation.
 - Review existing menus quarterly to decide which menus sell well and which does not. For the menus that don't sell well it can be promoted to increase the sales. Otherwise, if it's still doesn't sell well, Pasundan can remove those menus.
 - One approach that can be taken is to provide a special menu for a special occasion. For example, Pasundan can provide Eid menu packages that can be targeted at Indonesian students and Indonesian citizens who live around the city of Nijmegen.

Price

- (ST2) Maintain the restaurant's reputation for friendly service and the food to combat the threat of inflation and potential price increase
 - If a service's perceived costs exceed its perceived benefits, the service has a negative net value and the consumer is unlikely to buy it (Wirtz and Lovelock, 2021). In order to maintain the restaurant's good reviews, effective communication from Pasundan is necessary to help customers comprehend the value they receive to control the perceived value. Communicate clearly with personal explanations if there will be delayed in delivery and provide helpful solution when there's incomplete order.

Place

- **(WO2) Collaborate with platforms like Uber Eats to broaden the distribution channels and reach a wider audience**
 - According to Gelder (2023), Uber Eats was the second most downloaded online food and delivery takeaway app in 2022, with over 46 million app downloads. Based on preliminary research, some customers prefer Uber Eats to Thuisbezorgd, with the majority of them being internationals. Pasundan can reach wider audience by partnering with Uber Eats.

Promotion

- **(WO1) Improve digital marketing efforts to increase the restaurant's online presence, and capitalize on the large number of internet and social media users in the Netherlands, (SO1) Focus on emphasizing brand and product on social media.**
 - Create content on social media such as Facebook and Instagram to branding Pasundan's authenticity, longevity, and point of differences (PoD) from competitors
 - Highlight the authenticity and the family recipe by posting a storytelling carousel on Instagram
 - Collaborate with local Key Opinion Leader (KOL) to increase awareness and engagement. @tastenijmegen is an account that provides information about where to eat and drink in Nijmegen. The account is owned by Olesia and is available both on TikTok and Instagram. She has 16.3k followers on Instagram and 5318 followers on TikTok
- **(SO3) Utilize the positive customer reviews and achievement to create a loyal customer**
 - Create weekly content by posting stories and feed on Instagram about customer reviews. The purpose of this post is to assist customers that the reviews on other platforms (Google and Tripadvisor) are aligned with restaurant's account
 - Create a content to educate the customers by giving them information about products and menus at Pasundan. This strategy is expected to provide clearer information so that it can assist consumer decision making in choosing a restaurant and the menus
- **(SO4) Promote the family recipe and authenticity of the Indonesian cuisine to attract Dutch people who are open to other cuisines**
 - According to psychology of menu, applying names of mothers, grandmothers, and other relatives (e.g., Opa Bert's Special Rendang) has been demonstrated to attract customers to order that item (Wirtz and Lovelock, 2021). This strategy will also enhance the branding strategy to promote authenticity and family vibes
 - Add the recommendation and best seller logos on the menu to assist customers in deciding which meal to order. According to the findings, many Dutch customers are unfamiliar with several of the unique Indonesian menus. It can be difficult to choose menu that they're not familiar with. As a result, many menus do not sell well. Customers can get extra information by placing little badges.
- **(WT2) Engage in more promotion activities to beat competitors and (WT1) attract new market**
 - Applying selective price discount, Pasundan can give special offer for student such as student menu, student discount, etc. Another example is monthly deals for selected menu with discounted price for particular market (eg. Special price for Nasi Kuning menu for Indonesian on Indonesia independence's day
 - Promote the vegetarian and vegan menu on social media to attract more vegan and vegetarian customers

People

- **(ST1) Use its strong foundation of loyal customers and positive reviews to counter the threat of competitors with similar products**
 - Greet customers warmly and if possible use customer's name. The front of staff can give Indonesian touch by greeting them with "Selamat Datang" and "Terima Kasih" after they paid to create Indonesian atmosphere and enhance the authenticity
 - Give personalized recommendations based on customers' diet restriction, taste preferences, or previous order to show the attentiveness and care about their dining experiences
 - Treat customers like family and engage in friendly conversation when appropriate to create personal connection
 - Remember and recall their previous visits (favorite dishes or drinks) and acknowledge their loyalty, thus customers may feel valued and appreciated

Physical Evidence

- **(SO2) Display the award logo from Restaurant Guru**
 - Award logo "The Best Vegetarian Restaurant" given by Restaurant Guru can be displayed in front of the restaurant. Thus, people can see the achievement
 - Play Indonesian music to enhance the authenticity vibes. Hence old Dutch customers or Indonesian customers can feel nostalgic as well. This can also enhance the branding strategy for the authenticity

Process

- **(WO3) Actively monitor online review, respond to negative review quickly**
 - Pasundan can encourage its customers to complain directly to the restaurant before writing a negative online review. However, if a negative online review has been written, then Pasundan should respond quickly and attentively to that review. The responses given can be in the form of solutions that can be offered to existing problems
- **(WT4) Establish SOP thus Pasundan can enhance better services to compete with competitors**
 - Pasundan can develop blueprint of the process starting from pre-process stage, in-process stage, to post-purchase stage. A good blueprint should highlight the points in service delivery where things are most likely to go wrong (Wirtz and Lovelock, 2021).
 - Improve customer communication channels by providing regular updates on order status and anticipated delays
 - Define roles and responsibilities clearly, including particular tasks for dealing with online orders, phone orders, dine-in customers, and takeout
 - Implement a system for properly prioritizing and managing orders, ensuring that both front-of-house and kitchen staff understand order priorities and timelines
 - Encourage employees to double-check orders and emphasise the significance of accuracy over speed during peak hours.
 - Create order checklist form to assist the front of house staff to recheck all the orders before give it to delivery guy to be sent. This tool will help to guarantee that all order components are complete and correct.

CONCLUSION

The author proposed several business solutions to solve Pasundan's current business issue. Pasundan should concentrate on improving their food delivery process. First and foremost, Pasundan can develop new SOPs so that the employees can double-check the order and maintain clear communication across divisions. Pasundan should invest more in promotion activities, particularly social media marketing, to compete with competitors and raise brand awareness. The reason is because about 70% of the Dutch population uses social media. By utilising social media marketing, Pasundan can emphasise its strengths and point of differences. To reach more customers, Pasundan should broaden its distribution channel by partnering with Uber Eats. Pasundan also should maintain the restaurant's good reputation by improving the service given by their people. Although this research may provide valuable insights to marketing mix strategy in the restaurant business, it still has limitations. Additional research is needed, particularly in the operating area, to have a greater comprehension of service quality and the food service process. This study has several limitations considering the consumer analysis was done solely through the analysis of online reviews. Future research would provide more detailed information regarding marketing strategy, allowing restaurants to design more effective marketing campaigns. Moreover, future research can use combination of quantitative and qualitative methods, and conduct interviews or questionnaire to larger group.

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